

THE PURPOSE AND TASKS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL READING CLASSES

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Annotation: this article talks about the purpose and tasks of reading classes. Qualifications that students should acquire are recorded.

Keywords: study lessons, student, task, knowledge, skill, qualification

Primary education serves as a foundation in creating a creative person who will raise the future of Uzbekistan to the level of a great country. The main goal of a primary school teacher is to ensure that students are educated and have a wide range of thinking. Analyzing their data and making it widely available. In primary classes, where the child's mind and thinking are being formed, the skills of the teacher, his skillful application of modern technologies to the educational process, skillful use of advanced pedagogical experiences, and the use of new methods of teaching are very important. is enough. Article 9 of the Law "On Education" of September 23, 2020 is dedicated to the teaching of classes I-IV. Clause 3.3.1 of the "National program of personnel training in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated October 6, 1997 shows plans for the organization of training in grades I-IV in the development of continuous education. The principle and setting of new goals for school education leads to a radical change in the content of mathematics education. Another issue that does not lose its relevance and importance for us is the task of raising our children as truly patriotic people with independent thinking, modern knowledge and skills, with a solid life position.

Specific topics included in the elementary school "Reading Book" textbooks are determined by the fact that they introduce students to the magical world of fiction, and focus on the correct formation of their worldviews based on the ideology of national independence. Accordingly, the leading feature of the reading classes is to ensure students' literacy, and to educate them in the spirit of high moral values based on the national ideology. The subject range of the works studied in the reading classes of primary grades is quite wide, they are within the framework of general topics such as mother nature, seasons, folklore, love of work, major holiday dates, national independence and spirituality. combined.

Reading classes of primary grades have a special place in the education system according to their essence, goals and tasks. After all, it is the foundation of literacy and moral education. That is why the education of other subjects cannot be imagined without the education of reading.

The student is faced with the ability to read the text correctly, quickly, understand it, and master its content for the first time in the reading classes. Through the reading classes, the way is opened for students to acquire educational skills and knowledge that are expected to be mastered by the requirements of the State Education Standard (DTS). It is precisely in reading education that a person's aspirations to understand himself, and secondly, the world, are stimulated. For this purpose, the "Reading book" textbooks include various topics such as

mother nature, the world around us, the history and current image of our country, the lives of adults and children, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship between nations and peace. artistic, moral-educational, scientific popular works intended to provide detailed understanding of

The main task of teaching the subject of reading (grades 1-4): - to ensure the formation and development of the oral speech of students based on the standards of the literary language, to develop speech competence; - development of skills and competences of high literacy, adherence to literary language standards, use of stylistic variety, firstly familiar, then unfamiliar text expression is taught, the student's skills and competence are determined. Quantitative indicators are also determined - reading speed, conscious and fluent reading, how many words can be read per minute.

In the 3rd and 4th grade curriculum, the scope of topics is much wider. In these classes, most of the reading lessons are focused on reading and working on the text. In the lesson, using methods that increase the student's activity and enrich their imagination, using positive tasks such as reading the novel based on the content of the genre, dividing it into roles, retelling the story on behalf of the characters, continuing the story about the hero's fate, creating an oral story on interesting topics. such things are done. Reading lessons in the classroom perform the following tasks: 1. Improving reading skills. Good reading qualities in students: formation of correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading skills. 2. To instill in children a love for books, to use books, to get the necessary knowledge from them, that is, to cultivate deep-thinking, thoughtful readers who know how to work with books. Cultivating thoughtful, reflective readers. 3. Expanding students' knowledge about the environment and existence, forming the elements of worldview. 4. Educate students in the spirit of moral-aesthetic and hard work. 5. Developing students' speech and thinking. 6. Formation of elements of literary imagination. There must be a clear way to accomplish these tasks. Qualities of Good Reading Skills and Ways to Improve Them Qualities of good reading skills include reading accurately, quickly, consciously, and expressively, and they are interdependently improved in reading lessons, which The four reading qualities are inextricably linked. Conscious reading is the main thing, because if the student reads by himself and does not understand what he has read, then such reading does not meet the requirements, it leads to not understanding what he has read. Correct reading serves conscious reading. Fast, accurate, conscious reading is the basis of expressive reading. Acquiring good reading skills is a condition for successfully mastering all subjects at school. The reading skill is a complex skill, and methodist T.G. Egorov divides its formation process into 3 stages:

1. Analytical stage (reading). Literacy is part of the teaching process. It develops children's ability to read words in syllables.
2. Synthetic stage (reading). At this stage, the ability to read words by heart is formed. In this case, by seeing the word, its sound side is perceived. Understanding the meaning of a word is compatible with its pronunciation. Based on Sidirga reading, students pass in the 3rd grade.
3. Automated reading. In this reading, the reader reads according to the beginning of the word. It corresponds to the next years of study. In the 4th grade, some students' reading becomes automatic.

Reading lessons should be organized in such a way that the analysis of the content is directed to the improvement of good reading skills. One of the qualities of good reading skills is reading correctly. Several Methodist scholars have defined the correct reading:

K. Kasimova: correct reading is reading without making mistakes. Expanding this definition: the correct reading is the sound-letter composition of the word, without breaking the grammatical form, without omitting any sound or syllable in the word, without adding an extra sound or syllable. without shmas, without changing the place of the letters, reading according to the stress of the word is the correct reading. M.Odilova, T.Ashrapova say: "All the requirements set for the norms of literary pronunciation also apply to the ability to read correctly." So, according to them, reading the material in accordance with the norms of literary pronunciation is called correct reading. Russian Methodist Yakovleva: "Correct reading is to copy the material by sound without error and smoothly." The essence of all 3 definitions is the same. That is, correct reading is reading the sound structure of the word without breaking the grammatical form, based on the norms of literary and orthoepic pronunciation. Elementary school students have difficulty synthesizing the meaning of the text with the correct pronunciation. To improve reading skills, it is necessary to work on the work together with teaching.

Relying on life experiences and observations based on the requirements of the state, the reading lessons will ensure their conscious perception of its effectiveness. Educational and educational goals of reading and speech development, methods of developing oral and written speech of reading skills by classes, connection of reading activities with written speech such issues are clearly included. Reading classes in primary grades create the initial basis for mastering Uzbek literature, history, geography, biology and other subjects in higher grades. Therefore, it is necessary to pay serious attention to reading lessons in primary grades.

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